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The God of Small Things: A Literary Critique of la fratellanza in ‘God’s Own Country’

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Abstract: Deliberating on the concept of neighbour, in his 2020 encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, Pope Francis talks about the importance of becoming a neighbour to others by being “present to those in need of help, regardless of whether or not they belong to our social group.” Becoming a neighbour – it is easier said than done even by a society that is known for its exemplary human and social development, a Christian community that grew up on the parable of the *Good Samaritan* for close to two millennia, and a political system that not only promises but arguably fights for an egalitarian society. Detailing the sequence of events leading to the tragedy of Velutha, an ‘untouchable Christian’ and the

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ensuing fall of a ‘touchable Syrian Christian’ family, in her novel, *The God of Small Things*, Arundhati Roy depicts the failure of a society, a religion and a political system to become a neighbour to a person in need of help. In the light of *Fratelli Tutti*, this article analyses Roy’s depiction and critique of that triple failure in ‘God’s own country,’ Kerala.

Keywords: Syrian Christians, Caste System, Untouchables, Communist Party, Discrimination, Reform, Tragedy.

Introduction: On Becoming a Neighbour

The tragic plot of Arundhati Roy’s Booker Prize winning 1997 novel, *The God of Small Things*, unfolds through the reminiscences, associations and anticipations of the unfortunate sequence of events that took place in the Ipe family in 1969, and the account of what happens in the same family in the narrative present in 1993. The story is set in Ayemenem, a village in ‘God’s own country,’ Kerala, infamous for its caste-based social inequality and discrimination. While the Indian caste system (the theoretical basis of all forms of discriminations in India), dating back to about three thousand years, rests comfortably and complacently on the Eastern theological foundations of *dharma* (duty) and *karma* (work or action), it enjoys sanctification by the Hindu scriptural text, the *Purusha Sukta* of the *Rigveda*. Manu’s ancient text on dharma, the *Manusmriti*, which offers a schematic commentary on the caste system, serves as the fine print to what is said about this inequitable and unjust hierarchical system in the *Rigveda*. One main reason for the tragic turn of events in the novel is that God’s own country’s version of the unjust caste system is supported and promoted silently by the opportunistic Communists while they preach about an egalitarian society and adhered to by the Christians who teach the world that one should love one’s neighbour as oneself.

Paradoxically, this social tragedy unfolds in a county that abolished caste-based inequality and discrimination in 1950, in a society that is predominantly Hindu, in a milieu that is essentially Christian and in a political backdrop that is noticeably Communist. Discourses pertaining to society, culture, religion and politics converge at Ayemenem to ensure the death of a man who dared to defy the prevailing love laws, because, for many, such “a man’s death could be more profitable than his life had ever been” (Roy, 1997: 281). A poignant image at the heart of the novel set in this heartless world is that of the semi-conscious Velutha, one of the protagonists, brutalised by police, “abandoned by God and History; by Marx, by Man, by Woman, and—in the hours to come—by Children, lay[ing] folded on the floor” at Kottayam police station waiting to breathe his last (Roy, 1997: 310).

His skull was fractured in three places. His nose and both his cheekbones were smashed, leaving his face pulpy, undefined. The blow to his mouth had split open his upper lip and broken six teeth, three of which were embedded in his lower lip, hideously inverting his beautiful smile. Four of his ribs were splintered, one had pierced his left lung, which was what made him bleed from his mouth. The blood on his breath bright red. Fresh. Frothy. His lower intestine was ruptured and haemorrhaged, the blood collected in his abdominal cavity. His spine was damaged in two places, the concussion had paralyzed his right arm and resulted in a loss of control over his bladder and rectum. Both his kneecaps were shattered (Roy, 1997: 310).

This brutalised image of Velutha reminds us of the traveller who was attacked, robbed and abandoned by the robbers, as well as ignored by both the Priest and the Levite in the biblical *Parable of the Good Samaritan*. Deliberating on the Parable, in passing,

Pope Francis mentions in his 2020 encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti* (Brothers and Sisters All) a famous anecdote from the life of Hillel, the Jewish Rabbi of 1 BCE. As per the anecdote, once a heathen told the Rabbi that he would gladly accept Jewish faith if the Rabbi could teach him the entire Torah standing on one foot. Hillel stood on one foot and said quoting Tobit 4:15, “Never do to others what you don’t want them to do to you. This is the entire Torah. Everything else is commentary. Go and live it” (Outcalt, 2015: 62). According to Francis, when Jesus says, “do to others whatever you would that others do to you: there you have the Law and the Prophets” (Mt 7:12), he is endorsing Hillel’s teaching. This command of Jesus is “universal in scope ... [because, it embraces] everyone on the basis of our shared humanity” (Francis, 2020: 50).

The Priest and the Levite in the Parable are people dedicated to the worship of God. Their striking indifference to the suffering of the man who fell into the hands of robbers is the affirmation “that belief in God and the worship of God are not enough to ensure that we are actually living in a way pleasing to God” (Francis, 2020: 58). Jesus came up with the parable in answer to the question as to who should be considered as one’s neighbour. Probably, Jesus would have come up with the same parable if he were asked who should be considered as one’s brother or sister. The term, ‘neighbour,’ at the time of Jesus in Jewish society was used to refer to those close to us. Redefining the meaning of the term, ‘neighbour,’ Jesus “asks us to not decide who is close enough to be our neighbour, but rather that we ourselves become neighbours to all” (Francis, 2020: 63). In fact, “Jesus asks us to be present to those in need of help, regardless of whether or not they belong to our social group” (Francis, 2020: 63). Similarly, extending the meaning of the term, ‘neighbour,’ to the terms, ‘brother’ and ‘sister,’ Jesus would be asking us to be brothers and sisters to everyone

regardless of whether or not they belong to our immediate family. To be a neighbour to someone and thereby be a brother or sister, one must learn to see all as *Fratelli Tutti* – as brothers and sisters all.

Roy's multivalent novel, *The God of Small Things*, may be read as a critique on the failure of a society, a religion and a political system to function as a brother, a sister and a neighbour to those in need of help, epitomised in the novel's tragic protagonists, Velutha and Ammu. The Indian and the Keralite society that boast of their belief in the philosophy of 'vasudhaiva kutumbakam (the world is one family) and teaches their children to regard all Indians as their brothers and sisters, the Ipe family in the novel functioning as the microcosm of Kerala's Syrian Christian community that has grown up on the *Parable of the Good Samaritan* for two millennia, as well as the Communist Party that vows by the ideology of comradeship — all fail equally and deliberately. In the spirit of the universal brotherhood and sisterhood expounded in Francis's *Fratelli Tutti*, this article will analyse Roy's depiction and critique in *The God of Small Things* of this indefensible failure of a society (Keralite society), a religion (Christianity) and a political system (Kerala's Communist political system) to become a brother, a sister, and a neighbour to all, especially to the underprivileged and the vulnerable members of the human family.

1. On a Society's Failure to Become a Neighbour

The caste system, also called the varna system, which assigned the members of Hindu society to an impermeable hierarchical structure, is not only one of the most ancient and unjust social structures in the world, but also the most perilous fiction that has ever been said about humanity. The *Rigveda* traces the origin of the caste system to the mythical act and time of creation when the Brahmins were born from the mouth of Purusha (the Primeval Man or the Cosmic Being who sacrificed himself), the Kshatriyas from his arms, the Vaishyas from his thighs, and the Sudras from his feet. On account of their imagined origin from the mouth of

Purusha, the Brahmins are regarded as superior to the rest. The Kshatriyas are superior to the Vaishyas and Sudras, though inferior to the Brahmins; and the Vaishyas are superior to the Sudras though inferior to the Brahmins and Kshatriyas. Sudras, owing to their origin from the feet of Purusha, ended up as inferior to all the other three groups. During the later Vedic period, those born of inter-caste unions were assigned the status of the Outcasts or the Untouchables (known today as the Scheduled Castes). They were not part of the four-fold caste system; and they ranked below the Sudras in social status. To added insult to injury, the discourse of the retributive *karma* asserted that one's berth into a lower caste is the just punishment for the sins that one committed in one's previous life.

People were to perform duties to society in accordance with their birth. Therefore, while the Brahmins performed the duties of the priests, the Kshatriyas performed those of the military and political personnel, the Vaishyas of the cultivators, herders and merchants, and the Sudras of the servants in society. The Outcasts or the Untouchables were assigned the supposedly polluting duties such as tanning hides, scavenging, disposal of dead animals, preparing dead bodies for cremation and so on that people belonging to the caste system did not want to perform. Over the centuries, different vulnerable sections of society who performed such duties for their livelihood, solely for lack of other alternatives, also came to be regarded as Untouchables.

The name *candala* was originally the name of one such indigenous tribe. Its first appearance in the source material occurred during the Later Vedic Era but was not equated with untouchability. As their untouchability developed over time, all people associated with their way of life came to be referred to as *candalas*. Some members of Aryan agrarian

society were also added to their ranks by virtue of occupation, crime or vagabondage (Yamazaki, 1997: 12).

Even though the caste system in Kerala is rather different from that of the rest of India, until the middle of the twentieth century, Kerala had been a hotbed of caste-based social inequality and discrimination. While the conventional Kshatriyas and the Vaisyas are conspicuously absent in Kerala, the Nayars (whom the Brahmins in Kerala considered as Sudras) took the place of Kshatriyas. The Ezhavas ranked below the Nayars; and the slave castes ranked below the Ezhavas (Kurien, 2002: 45). Some historians are of the view that as elite merchants and traders, the Syrian Christians ranked somewhere between the Kshatriyas and the Vaisyas (Frykenberg, 2000: 155). Similarly, as traders, the Jews and some Muslims also seemed to have occupied the social position of the Vaisya caste. Despite being considered the Sudra caste, ranking just below the Brahmin caste, the Nayars were looked upon as an upper caste. Even though the Ezhavas performed the duties of the Sudras, they were regarded as untouchables (Kurien, 2002: 32). The predicament of the Untouchables until the early decades of the twentieth century had been rather dreadful. Recalling the wretched plight of the Untouchable Paravans during the years of her girlhood, in *The God of Small Things*, Mammachi tells her grandchildren, Estha and Rahel:

Paravans were expected to crawl backwards with a broom, sweeping away their footprints so that Brahmins or Syrian Christians would not defile themselves by accidentally stepping into a Paravan's footprint. In Mammachi's time, Paravans, like other Untouchables, were not allowed to walk on public roads, not allowed to cover their upper bodies, not allowed to carry umbrellas. They had to put their hands over their mouths when they spoke, to divert their polluted

breath away from those whom they addressed
(Roy, 2014: 73-74).

Shocked by the prevailing caste-based social inequality and discrimination that he witnessed in Kerala during his visit to the place in 1892, Swami Vivekananda writes, “Was there ever a sillier thing before in the world than what I saw in Malabar country? ... these Malabaris are all lunatics, their homes so many lunatic asylums ... Shame upon them that such wicked and diabolical customs are allowed” (Vivekananda, 1955-1960: 294). In the nineteenth and the early twentieth century, Christians with an untouchable lineage were not allowed to enter even the churches of the Syrian Christians. At the time of Vivekananda’s visit, the revival movements in the realms of religion, culture, politics, economics, literature and social consciousness in Kerala, known as *Kerala navodhanam* (Kerala Renaissance), initiated by the lower caste people, was gaining momentum. The unprecedented changes that followed the revival movement would place Kerala ahead of the rest of India in social cohesion as well as in development indicators such as life expectancy, literacy, healthcare, education, public health and so on. Nevertheless, the remnants of the evils of the caste system would continue to linger on in Kerala. The narrative of *The God of Small Things* is set at Ayemenem, a village in the ‘reformed Kerala’ of 1969 where caste-based discrimination was still prevalent. Born in 1961, and raised in Kerala, Arundhati Roy recalls her experience of growing up in Ayemenem plagued by the caste-based discrimination.

I grew up with my mother in a Syrian Christian family in Ayemenem, a small village in communist-ruled Kerala. And yet all around me were the fissures and cracks of caste. Ayemenem had its own separate ‘Paraiyan’ church where ‘Paraiyan’ priests preached to an ‘Untouchable’

congregation. Caste was implied in people's names, in the way people referred to each other, in the work they did, in the clothes they wore, in the marriages that were arranged, in the language they spoke (Roy, 2014: 13).

Even though the days of the Untouchables having to crawl backward with brooms were over by 1969, subjugation, deprivation and discrimination based on birth and caste were a reality even then. Velutha and his family in the novel are Paravans (members of a fishing community that ended up as part of the untouchable sections of south India). The Syrian Christian Ipe family's patriarch, "Pappachi would not allow Paravans into the house. Nobody would. They were not allowed to touch anything that Touchables touched. Caste Hindus and Caste Christians" (Roy, 1997: 73). If born an Untouchable, unfortunately, one could not improve one's social and financial status in the caste-ridden society in India. Hence, Pappachi's wife, "Mammachi (with impenetrable Touchable logic) often said that if only ... [Velutha] hadn't been a Paravan, he might have become an engineer. He mended radios, clocks, water pumps. He looked after the plumbing and all the electrical gadgets in the house" (Roy, 1997: 75). In the 'reformed Kerala,' engineering is certainly not meant for Velutha because, he is a Paravan! Despite Velutha being an Indian, his society denies him the fundamental rights that the constitution of India guarantees to every Indian citizen. As Francis affirms, "it is unacceptable that the mere place of one's birth or residence [or caste] should result in his or her possessing fewer opportunities for a developed and dignified life" (88).

The narrator of the novel comments on the predicament of the disadvantaged people like Velutha saying that Velutha's "lack of hesitation," his "unwarranted assurance," "the way he walked," "the way he held his head," the way he offered unsolicited suggestions, "the quiet way in which he disregarded suggestions without appearing to rebel" were laudable qualities in a person belonging to an upper caste. However, "in a Paravan they could

(and would, and indeed, should) be construed as insolence” (Roy, 1997: 76). As Francis says, when it comes to the vulnerable sections of society, “the law is no longer seen as reflecting a fundamental notion of justice but as mirroring notions currently in vogue ... everything is ‘leveled down’ by a superficial bartered consensus. In the end, the law of the strongest prevails” (152). In the case of Velutha, the law did not behave differently.

Velutha’s supposed ‘crime’ in the novel is that being an ‘Untouchable Christian,’ he dares to love Ammu, a Syrian Christian woman, an upper caste Christian woman, ‘a touchable woman’ against the love laws of the land. Their love is physical in nature. Though Velutha and Ammu are consenting adults as well as Christians, their love is seen as a crime in which Velutha stands to lose everything. As per the rule in *Manusmriti*, “A man who corrupts an unwilling virgin should instantly suffer corporal or capital punishment; but a man who corrupts a willing (virgin) when he is her equal should not undergo corporal or capital punishment ... If a man of the rear castes makes love with a virgin of the highest caste, he should be given corporal or capital punishment” (Manu, 1991: 159). Therefore, Vellya a Paapen, Velutha’s father, who though a Christian, has internalised the specifics of the appalling laws of Manu, waits “for hours at the door of their hut ... the edge of his axe glittering in the lamplight, waiting for Velutha to return” so that he himself could put his lawbreaking son to death (Roy, 1997: 283). As Francis asks, “What is law without the conviction, born of age-old reflection and great wisdom, that each human being is sacred and inviolable” (150-51). The Kottayam police almost completes the task that Vellya a Paapen undertakes but is unable to do. “Murder is not wrong simply because it is socially unacceptable and punished by law, but because of a deeper conviction” (Francis, 2020: 150-51) that “Human life, as a gift of God, is sacred and inviolable” (Paul II, 1995: 67).

As the clandestine relationship between Velutha and Ammu comes to light, in order to protect their supposed ‘family honour,’ the Ipe family files a trumped-up FIR at Kottayam police station stating that Velutha tried to rape Ammu; and after the former was dismissed from his job in their factory for misconduct, he came to their house drunk one late evening and threatened the women in family; and later, he abducted three of their children and murdered one of them, namely, Sophie Mol. Inspector Thomas Mathew who handles the investigation regarding the case knows well that the charges are false and Velutha is innocent. However, the unprincipled pragmatic in him persuades him to close his eyes against the obvious, realising that “He had a Touchable wife, two Touchable daughters – whole Touchable generations waiting in their Touchable wombs...” (Roy, 1997: 259). Therefore, Thomas Mathew sets his police force on Velutha “to square the books and collect the dues from those who broke its laws” (Roy, 1997: 308). After breaking his teeth, ribs and skull, the police handcuff Velutha and take him into their custody where he will succumb to his injuries. The narrator of the novel comments on the police brutality saying, “Man’s subliminal urge to destroy what he could neither subdue nor deify ... It was human history, masquerading as God’s Purpose, revealing herself to an under-age audience” (Roy, 1997: 308-8). The narrator goes on to say that by doing what the police did, “They were merely inoculating a community against an outbreak” (Roy, 1997: 309). Velutha’s crime – being a free citizen of a free country, he loves a consenting woman of age socially superior to him. For loving the woman, he is accused of breaking the supposedly sacrosanct love laws. His crime is interpreted as an ‘outbreak’ even by the police! “Ask any village policeman in India what his job is and he’ll probably tell you it is to ‘keep the peace.’ That is done, most of the time, by upholding the caste system. Dalit aspirations are a breach of peace” (Roy, 2014: 14). Commenting on the failure of the police personnel to function as agents of justice, as brothers, sisters and neighbours to Velutha, the narrator says:

If they [the policemen] hurt Velutha more than they intended to, it was only because any kinship, any connection between themselves and him, any implication that if nothing else, at least biologically he was a fellow creature—had been severed long ago. They were not arresting a man, they were exorcising fear. They had no instrument to calibrate how much punishment he could take. No means of gauging how much or how permanently they had damaged him. (Roy, 1997: 309).

The fear that the agents of law and order try to exorcise by fatally torturing Velutha is nothing more than what Francis terms as “a kind of ‘local’ narcissism unrelated to a healthy love of one’s own people and culture. It is born of a certain insecurity and fear of the other that leads to rejection and the desire to erect walls for self-defence” (107). The tragedy of Velutha and Ammu is a testimony to the failure of society towards its vulnerable members who need its protection, care and compassion. It is a reminder to all that “as our minds and hearts narrow, the less capable we become of understanding the world around us” (Francis, 2020:108) and the less conscious we become of the needs of our brothers, sisters and neighbours and our responsibility towards them.

2. On a Religion’s Failure to Become a Neighbour

The common profile of Christians as spelt out by St. Paul in Galatians 3: 26-28 tells us that in Christ Jesus all are children of God through faith; all who were baptized into Christ have clothed themselves with Christ. Therefore, among Christians, there is no room for any form of segregation or discrimination based on nationality, language, culture, caste, class, gender or any other parameter. All are one in Christ Jesus.

However, the Syrian Christians in Kerala would not easily look upon their brothers and sisters from the lowest strata of Hindu society baptised into Christ like themselves as their equals. The Christian faith they received from the disciple of Christ himself and the Christian tradition they pride themselves in fail to make them recognise their disadvantaged fellow humans as their brothers, sisters and neighbours. Unfortunately, as Francis argues, “A believer may be untrue to everything that his faith demands of him, and yet think he is close to God and better than others” (58-59). What makes a true Christian is not such convenient and self-righteous attitude, but rather, as Francis affirms, “an authentic openness to God ... [which] is a way of practising the faith that helps open our hearts to our brothers and sisters” (59). In adherence to the vile upper caste Hindu practice of caste-based social discrimination and untouchability, the Syrian Christians also look upon certain vulnerable and disadvantaged sections of society not only as inferior to them, but also as Untouchables, as if the latter were children of a lesser god. Does this not amount to masking, misrepresenting, manipulating and distorting the fundamental truths of Christian identity and faith? History can certainly prove how right Francis is in saying that unless we “learn to unmask the various ways that the truth is manipulated, distorted and concealed in public and private discourse ... those fundamental human rights which we now consider unassailable will be denied by those in power, once they have gained the ‘consensus’ of an apathetic or intimidated population” (151).

The privileged Syrian Christian community in the novel are depicted as active agents in denying Valutha, a less-privileged ‘Untouchable Christian,’ even his fundamental rights, let alone being a brother, sister, or a neighbour to him. These privileged Christians are certainly well informed about the fine prints of the fundamental rights; they have been conscious of what Francis reminds us: “The Book of Job sees our origin in the one Creator as the basis of certain common rights” (49); and they have been catechised about St. Paul’s teaching on the common profile of

Christians. However, their moral blindness does not permit them to consider Velutha as a brother, a neighbour and fellow Christian who is also an integral part of the mystical body Christ of which they themselves are parts, not more, not less. The gravity of the failure of the Syrian Christian community towards Velutha gets intensified by the fact that it is a community that proudly claims its Christian roots to St. Thomas, the apostle of Christ, and hence, as old as Christianity itself. The narrative of *The God of Small Things* tells us how even after two millennia of its birth in Kerala, Christianity, in many ways, has failed to inculcate the spirit of the *Parable of the Good Samaritan* into its members.

The Ipe family, the immediate agent of social discrimination against Velutha, are members of the Mar Thoma Church, a group of Syrian Christians in Kerala. In order to understand the underlying dynamics of the hierarchical social relationship between the Ipe Family and Velutha's family, one must delve into the two-thousand-year-old history of Christianity in Kerala. Though there is little evidence to ascertain the historical accuracy of the arrival of St. Thomas in India, as per the traditional beliefs of the Syrian Christians and the accounts in *The Acts of St. Thomas*, the fourth-century Edessa-based Syriac apocryphal book of unknown origin, he came to Kerala, India, in AD 52. The Indo-Parthian King, Gundaphorus was responsible for his arrival in India (The Apocryphal Acts of Thomas, 2001: 53-54). The Syrian Christians in Kerala known as St. Thomas Christians, refer to *The Acts of St. Thomas* "as evidence for the antiquity of Christian traditions in south India and for missions that the apostle Thomas conducted there in the decades after the death of Jesus of Nazareth" (Andrade, 2018: 2). The historical proof for the existence of the trade routes between India and the eastern Mediterranean at the time of Christ is often cited for establishing the possibility of St. Thomas arrival in India (Tickell, 2007: 19). Many scholars are of the

opinion that the proven existence of the “trade routes that stretched from Roman territory deep into Asia and the Indian Ocean to strengthen this premise” (Andrade, 2018: 16).

During his stay and ministry in Kerala, St. Thomas is believed to have converted some Brahmin families to Christianity and established an Indian Christian community in the Southern peninsula of India. Deliberating on the arrival of Christianity in India, the narrator of the novel says that “Christianity arrived in a boat and seeped into Kerala like tea from a teabag” (33). After having seeped into Kerala, Christianity grew into a complex blend of tradition, culture and religion. Since the initial converts into Christianity were all Brahmins, they not only continued to maintain their supposed superior status and privileges in society, but also adhered to the caste equations of Hindu society even after they embraced Christianity. Therefore, contrary to Christian tenets, the community remained rather reluctant to accept new converts, especially those from the lower castes to their fold (Tickell, 2007: 20). Talking about the underlying complexity of the Syrian Christian community in Kerala, in his article, “Hindu in Culture, Christian in Religion, Oriental in Worship,” Placid Podipara, describes them as Indians in every aspect of their culture, Christian in their faith and Oriental Syriac in their worship (529). No wonder they too have been practitioners of the Indian caste system.

The fledgling Indian Church had little or no direct contact with the Church of Rome. However, right from its infancy, it maintained its communion with the Church of Rome through the Eastern Church (which would later be known as the East Syrian or Chaldean or Babylonian Church) centred on Seleucia-Ctesiphon, the capital of the Persian Empire. The relation between the early Indian Church based in Kerala and the Persian Church goes back to the fourth century. Commissioned by the Catholicos of Babylon, a group of Christian trading families from the Middle East, in all probability from Persia (the present-day Iran and Iraq) arrived in Kerala in 345 AD under the leadership

of Thomas of Jerusalem, known also as Thomas of Cana. The local Hindu king, Chroman Perumal, granted them settlement rights in the land (Frykenberg, 2000: 155). Under the influence of the of these Persian Christian families, the Indian Christian community would grow in their Christian faith further. Soon, the church in India, began to be guided and governed by the bishops of the Persian Church. From the early fourth century, the Patriarch of the Persian Church provided India with clergy, holy texts, and ecclesiastical infrastructure. Hence, under the Persian influence, the liturgy of the Church in Kerala developed along the line of Persian liturgy in Syriac language, a dialect of Aramaic language. Following the decline of the Church in Persia in the fourteenth century, the Church in India was effectively cut off from the former.

The arrival of Vasco da Gama, the Portuguese explorer and trader, in Kerala, in 1498, and the arrival of Portuguese missionaries, thereafter, opened a new chapter in the history of the Church in India. In Goa, the Portuguese set up a colonial government and a Latin Church hierarchy under the Archbishop of Goa. Empowered by the *Padroado Real* (a series of treaties and decrees in which the Pope conferred upon the king of Portugal certain authority in ecclesiastical matters in the foreign territories they conquered), the Portuguese began their missionary activities in India. They began converting Indians into Christianity. Jesuits, Franciscans and Carmelites were the missionaries in the forefront of this mission. In Kerala, the missionary activities of Francis Xavier, a great sixteenth-century Jesuit missionary among the fisher castes “led to the creation of the second major grouping, the Latin Christians” who followed the Latin rite liturgy in their worship (Fuller, 1976: 4).

The Portuguese-dominated Romanised Catholic Church in India looked upon the Eastern Church (the Persian Church),

so also the Church in Kerala, as adherents to the controversial Nestorian doctrine. In 1560, the Portuguese “tried to eradicate the Nestorian heresy and switch the allegiance of the Syrian church [in Kerala] from Antioch to Rome” (Fuller, 1976: 59) which resulted in the famous revolt of the Syrian Christians in Kerala epitomised in *Koonan Kurishu Satyam*, Great Oath of Bent Cross. A group of those who took part in the revolt went back to profess their allegiance to Rome “then the minority but now the majority, are known as Syrian Catholics” (Fuller, 1976: 59). The rest of the group entered into a new communion with the Syriac Orthodox Church of Antioch, to form an Oriental Orthodox Church (Malankara Orthodox Syrian Church). They pledged to be under the leadership of the Patriarch of Antioch. The bishop of this group of Christians took the name Mar Thoma. Influenced by the Anglican missionaries, under the leadership of Palakunnathu Abraham Malpan, some Christians from the Oriental Orthodox Church began a reform movement combining aspects of the Protestant reformation and aspects of the Eastern church. This movement grew into another church that came to be known as Mar Thoma Church. The Ipe family in *The God of Small Things* are members of Mar Thoma Church. As we are told in the first chapter of the novel, Reverend E. John Ipe (Punnyan Kunju), Ammu’s grandfather was a priest of the Mar Thoma Church.

Unable to endure the discrimination and exploitation by the upper caste Hindus, many lower caste Hindus have embraced other religions over the centuries. However, unfortunately, their predicament has not changed because, “caste prejudice in the subcontinent trumps religious belief. Though their scriptures do not sanction it, elite Indian Muslims, Sikhs and Christians all practise caste discrimination” (Roy, 2014: 27). As the British established their political supremacy in the southern peninsula of India in the early nineteenth century, they began converting the lower caste Hindus into the Anglican Church offering them money and food as incentives (Tickell, 2007: 21). During this third phase of missionary activities, to escape social discrimination and indignities, many belonging to the lowest

caste groups in Kerala embraced Christianity in the nineteenth and the early twentieth centuries. The narrator of the novel says that it was at this time that Velutha's grandfather, Kelan, along with "a number of Paravans, Pelayas and Pulayas" (74) joined the Anglican Church and became Christians. Those who became Christians at this point in history are essentially looked down upon by society, even by the Syrian Christian community, as a pariah church (Fuller, 1976: 4). These Christians are often referred to as 'New Christians' with a derogatory connotation. If it was their desire to escape the prevailing caste-based discrimination in Hindu society that attracted them to Christianity, the material benefits that the Anglican Church promised them came as an added incentive which earned them the derogatory epithet, 'Rice Christians.' Since the constitution of India excluded the Scheduled Caste converts to Christianity from getting the benefits of the programme of 'reservation,' as the narrator informs us, they had a double disadvantage.

It didn't take them long to realize that they had jumped from the frying pan into the fire. They were made to have separate churches, with separate services, and separate priests. As a special favour they were even given their own separate Pariah Bishop. After Independence they found they were not entitled to any government benefits like job reservations or bank loans at low interest rates, because officially, on paper, they were Christians, and therefore casteless. It was a little like having to sweep away your footprints without a broom. Or worse, not being allowed to leave footprints at all (Roy, 1997: 74).

The Syrian Christians who continued to look upon the 'New Christians' not only as irreconcilably different from them,

but also as Untouchables were certainly not aliens to the spirit of the timeless message of Francis that “Those who look down on their own people tend to create within society categories of first and second class, people of greater or lesser dignity, people enjoying greater or fewer rights. In this way, they deny that there is room for everybody” (74). Regrettably, St. Paul’s affirmation that “there is nothing unclean in itself, it is only unclean for those who consider it unclean” (Rom 14:14) seems to have no impact on them. In irrational loyalty to the prevailing Hindu observance of purity and pollution, they are unwilling to allow these ‘New Christians’ “to touch anything that Touchables touched. Caste Hindus and Caste Christians” (Roy, 1997: 73). Though they have often heard the biblical assertion, “Not less than I, they too were formed in the womb by the same God who formed us all within our mothers” (Job 31:15), they refuse to pay heed to its message. Hence, they not only refuse to be a brother, sister or neighbour to Velutha, but also let him be murdered. In fact, they become active agents of his foul murder. Velutha’s unwarranted death is nothing short of the failure of Christianity itself.

3. On a Political System’s Failure to Become a Neighbour

Under the influence of Kerala Renaissance, the people of Kerala saw Communism as an antidote to the widespread social inequality in the state. To a great extent, “the widespread inequality in Kerala contributed to the Communist Party of India’s (CPI) success in Kerala” (Mahmood, 2017). Politically speaking, the election of the CPI to power in Kerala in 1957, may be regarded as the high point of Kerala Renaissance. As an earthly alternative to the Christian notion of the Kingdom of heaven, the followers of Karl Marx envisioned for the people a heaven on earth, a stateless and classless society of equals with equal opportunities. “Marxism was a simple substitute for Christianity. Replace God with Marx, Satan with the bourgeoisie, Heaven with a classless society, the Church with the Party, and the form and purpose of the journey remained similar. An obstacle race, with a

prize at the end” (Roy, 1997: 66). For many uneducated, poor landless agricultural labourers, the land and educational reforms that the CPIM government introduced came as a saving grace. No wonder, Marxism found acceptance among all classes and sections of people in Kerala. The leadership of the party as well as of the state passing through the hands of people ranging from EMS Namboodiripad to Pinarayi Vijayan is a testimony to the popular acceptance of the communist ideology by the people of Kerala.

In the novel, while Velutha, an ‘Untouchable Christian’ employee of Paradise Pickles & Preserves factory, is a card holding member of the Communist party, Chacko, its co-owner is a communist sympathiser who wants to organise the workers in his factory into a Union. At the same time, it must also be noted that many with vested interests, including the Syrian Christians, were averse to the communists and their administrative reforms, especially the Land Reform Act. As the narrator of the novel says, in “Kerala the Syrian Christians were, by and large, the wealthy, estate-owning ... feudal lords, for whom communism represented a fate worse than death. They had always voted for the Congress Party” (66). They were land-owners, traders and some of them even landlords and soldiers like the Nayars (Brown, 1956: 15) Quite complacent in their insulated world of comfort and security, in general, they were not proponents of change and reform in society.

Despite all the good that communism brought about in Kerala, it could not usher in a classless society. Often, the communists themselves are seen as perpetrators of discrimination based on caste. For instance, during a meeting between K.N.M. Pillai, the local communist leader, and Chacko, the former tells the latter that even the former’s wife, Kalyani, “will never allow Paravans and all that into her house. Never. Even I cannot persuade her. My own wife. Of

course inside the house she is Boss.” After making this statement, “He turned to her with an affectionate, naughty smile” (Roy, 1997: 278), with a sense of satisfaction and in appreciation of her conduct. Instead of rising above the caste-based inequitable social structure to bring about its promised heaven on earth, the Communist Party tried to maintain and manipulate this divisive structure for its own survival. The narrator of the novel makes a very pertinent observation in this regard:

As a reformist movement that never overtly questioned the traditional values of a caste-ridden, extremely traditional community. The Marxists worked from within the communal divides, never challenging them, never appearing not to. They offered a cocktail revolution. A heady mix of Eastern Marxism and orthodox Hinduism, spiked with a shot of democracy (66-7).

That is the reason why even though Velutha is an official card-holding member of the Communist Party and one of its committed workers, when he is implicated in crimes that he never committed, the party’s local leader, Pillai, refuses to help him despite being aware of Velutha’s innocence. Comrade Pillai, whom the narrator refers to as “Ayemenem’s own Crusader for Justice and Spokesman of the Oppressed” (303), tells Velutha who comes to seek his help in proving his innocence which alone can save his life, “Comrade, you should know that Party was not constituted to support workers’ indiscipline in their private life ... *It is not in the party’s interest to take up such matters. Individual’s interest is subordinate to the organisation’s interest*” (Roy, 1997: 287). Conveniently, the opportunistic Pillai refuses to let the Communist Party stand by Velutha, an innocent and helpless victim as well as a comrade. The local communist political system wilfully turned a deaf ear to Velutha’s desperate appeal; it let him be murdered. By omission of its responsibility, it becomes a willing participant in the murder of Velutha. Failure of a political system to be of assistance and to be a brother, sister

or neighbour to someone most in need of both! The narrator commends on this inexcusable failure saying, “And there it was again. Another religion turned against itself. Another edifice constructed by human mind, decimated by human nature” (287).

Conclusion

After Cane murdered Abel, when God asked Cane about his brother, in order to walk away from his guilt and his responsibility towards his brother, Cane asked God the proverbial rhetorical question, “Am I my brother’s keeper?” (Gen 4:9). Based on the story of Cane and Abel, we have the English phrase, ‘my brother’s keeper,’ which connotes to one’s responsibility towards, one’s siblings, one’s ‘neighbours,’ and fellow human beings in general because of our common origin and destiny as spelt out in the meditation on the ‘Principle and Foundation’ in the Spiritual Exercises of St. Ignatius of Loyola. We are all brothers and sisters — *Fratelli Tutti* — who together make the human family. Therefore, as members of the human family, everyone has a responsibility to transcend our world which has been “broken up into fragments by narrow domestic walls” (Tagore, 2002: 40) and reach out to others as brothers, sisters and neighbours. A failure to care for any one member of the human family is a failure towards the human family itself. Hence, the failure, be it of a society, a religion, and a political system to care for any person and become a brother, sister or neighbour is a failure to embody the spirit of *fratellanza* (brotherhood and sisterhood). Therefore, *The God of Small Things* may be read as a critique on the failure of ‘God’s Own Country’ in embodying the spirit of *Fratelli Tutti* in daily life, faith and practice.

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